

Article

Green Practices to the Owners and Management of Restaurant Business: an Empirical Study

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Dates of submission: 06.03.2024

Date of publication: 29.06.2024

Abstract: *Despite making a significant economic contribution, tourism today clearly has a negative influence on the environment. Along with other stakeholders, visitors are worried about environmental deterioration, and as their awareness of this issue grows daily, green practices in tourism are born. Restaurants can benefit from green practices by adopting them because they play a significant role in the tourism industry. The study focused on restaurants' given importance on green practices. The research's findings are obtained using a random sample technique, structured questionnaire interviews, and data editing in a reasonable way. The study explores that a poor number of restaurants can define green practice correctly but among them most of the restaurants have it consciously or unconsciously although such practices are not under full-fledged. Results also show that restaurants have a mixed grasp of environmental practices. Despite the fact that both owners and management understand the importance of environmental concerns, there is still a lack of instruments to fully execute them. The restaurant business must work together to prioritize and implement all practical green practices. In light of the restaurant industry's negative effects on the environment, this research stresses the need of immediate collective action in the face of rising tourism.*

Keywords: *Green Tourism; Green Management; Restaurant Business; Tourism Industry; Bangladesh*

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the environmental challenges facing our planet. Extreme concerning issues are climate change, global warming, deforestation, high energy consumption and pollution continues to rise. The business operations indirectly contribute to the effects of global warming, high energy consumption, consumption of large quantities of food supplies as well as the increment in food waste disposal (Krause, 1993; Han et al., 2011; Langgat, 2019; Asadi, et al., 2020). In discussion the contribution on the degradation of the environment by the tourism business Glem Kreag (2001) explores the generation of waste and pollution (*air, water, solid waste, noise, and Visual*) by the visitors. Now consumers have become more aware of environmental pollution (D'souza, Taghian, 2005), which leads to changes in their consumption behaviors (Laroche et al., 2001). For example, consumers want to buy eco-friendly products to protect our environment, and they are even willing to pay more for such products (Han et al., 2018, Liu et al., 2017). On the demand side, environmentally responsible consumption is increasing among restaurant consumers, with patronage

increasing at restaurants that implement green practices (Bacig, Young, 2019; S. Y. Jang et al., 2015; Moon, 2021). As more customers recognize the seriousness of environmental problems, the consumer choices are becoming more ecologically conscious as they purchase products and services that are environmentally friendly (Han et al., 2010). The restaurant industry, in particular, plays a significant role in the tourism sector, and its contribution to environmental degradation cannot be ignored. Kasim (2009) expresses that while the service industry, particular the hospitality sector, continues to grow in importance; it finds it cannot escape from its responsibility for contributing to environmental degradation and climate change.

The growth of the tourist industry has both beneficial and bad effects for Bangladesh and the Cox's Bazar area. In the context of Bangladesh's tourist boom, particularly in Cox's Bazar, well-planned environmentally conscious restaurant business is crucial. Therefore, the most pressing issue facing the tourist sector is developing a long-term strategy for management that satisfies the demands of all parties involved while simultaneously preserving the environment, promoting economic growth, and preserving cultural traditions.

The aim of this empirical study is to investigate the significance of green practices to the owners and management of restaurant businesses in the context of tourism. The research question for the study is "How much important of green practices to the owners and managers in the restaurant industry?" The question leads to the broader objective of the study is to assess the importance of green practices to the owners and managers of the restaurant. The specific objectives are measuring the awareness of the owners and management of green practices and evaluating the degree of importance of green practices to the owners and management. It is evident from the review of literature that no study is conducted on the problem that makes the sense of uniqueness of the current study. By conducting in-depth research, analyzing existing literature, and collecting primary data, this study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on sustainable practices within the restaurant industry. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research methods. The findings of the study will have implications for both theory and practice. From a theoretical standpoint, it will contribute to the existing literature on sustainable practices within the restaurant industry, filling gaps in knowledge and adding new insight. By exploring the motivations and challenges faced by owners and managers, this study will shed light on the decision-making processes behind the adoption of green practices. From a practical perspective, the findings will provide actionable recommendations for restaurant owners and managers, industry associations, and policymakers to enhance sustainability in the tourism sector. Moreover, it will contribute to raising awareness among consumers about the importance of supporting green restaurants, thereby promoting a sustainable culture.

At present for the climate change tourism industry throughout the world is concerned about the environmental issue. Conscious tourists are also worried about environmental pollution and the negative effect of restaurant business, as a part of tourism industry, on the environment. The tourists view stresses the tourism and restaurant business to rethink of influence of tourism on the environment. All sorts of stakeholders of the tourism industry are affected by the contamination. So, pollution by tourism activities is now a burning question toward the human-being. This study is the earliest and unique step to presenting the information about the green practices by the restaurant business in Bangladesh. Desire of the tourism businessman to attract more tourists can be achieved by adopting green practices. The defining problem of this study is a timely one and widespread from the sense of areas of consequence. Restaurants have to participate in this agendum to uphold its tourism business with global competition which simultaneously can contribute to the environment. Therefore, this article is accurately justified.

2. Literature Review

Nowadays, it's harder to look at the tourist sector without seeing its negative effects on the environment. The rise of "green practices" in the tourism industry is a direct result of the growing environmental consciousness of both tourists and other industry players. When it comes to this industry's major participants, restaurants are in a prime position to reap the rewards of green practices. The term "green practices" refers to a wide range of environmentally friendly actions taken by businesses to reduce their ecological footprint. These practices encompass various aspects of restaurant operations, such as waste management, energy efficiency, water conservation, sustainable sourcing, and employee training.

Implementing green practices not only helps in reducing environmental impact but also brings numerous benefits to restaurant businesses, increased customer loyalty, and enhanced competitiveness. According to Ryu et al. (2008), industry professionals recognized the importance of green practice as one of the components contributing to image of the company and that they believe the image of the company can be improved through executing green practices, which in the long-run will contribute to customer loyalty.

The study by Kim and Hall (2020) of Korean restaurants concentrated on the relationship between sustainability practices and customer loyalty. The study concluded that restaurants needed to consider practicing food sustainability and waste management beyond cost reduction since such practices had the potential of increasing the loyalty of the customers and the enjoyment of dining in a restaurant. Jeong, Jang (2013) state in their research paper that engaging in green practices not only helps restaurateurs obtain a socially responsible business and save long-term operating costs but also helps them gain competitive advantages such as possessing a positive image and reputation. Green practices, as a “value-added business strategy,” can greatly benefit a hospitality company (Kim et al., 2017). Most restaurants adopt green practices because it can help them with business performance such as; reduce operational costs (Schubert et al., 2010; Susskind, Ali, 2014), improve a business’ corporate image and customer ratings (Hu et al., 2010; Namkung, Jang, 2013; Peiró-Signes et al., 2014), increase consumers’ purchasing and word-of-mouth intentions (Barber, Deale, 2014; Manaktola, Jauhari, 2007), and foster long-term success of a company’s financial performance (Singal, 2014).

The restaurant industry is far from being good for the environment. Restaurants generate enormous quantities of food waste, plastic waste, and emissions while simultaneously consuming huge quantities of water and energy (Kasim, Ismail, 2012). In their research Kim et al. (2020) claim that the restaurant industry is a huge generator of food waste and other resources, resulting in substantial greenhouse gas (GHG) pollution, material wastage, and huge massive investment costs. The restaurant business is one of those that use a lot of electricity, as well as a lot of water, cleaning equipment, and disposables such as to go containers. This large and reckless use of conventional resources makes the restaurant industry release a huge amount of carbon mission that pollutes the environment while maintaining the ambience for their customers (Szuchnicki, 2009).

Restaurants are responsible for a variety of “non-green” practices like the generation of food waste (Chiang, Sheu, 2020; Filimonau et al., 2020; Hatjiathanassiadou et al., 2019; Heikkilä et al., 2016), usage of non-sustainable materials in packaging and service delivery (Fieschi, Pretato, 2018; Tenenbaum, 2019), bad waste disposal strategies (Filimonau et al., 2020), and wasteful practices leading to the inefficient use of energy and water (Hatjiathanassiadou et al., 2019). Thus, there is a pressing need to explore and understand the importance of green practices to the owners and management of restaurant businesses in the context of tourism.

Batat (2020) opines that researchers emphasize that the industry should promote eco-friendly and responsible business practices to support sustainability, as the hospitality sector that including hotels and restaurants, contributes extensively to climate change by generating pollution, wasting energy and by using plastics and other harmful detergents and chemicals, and so on. Tourism is a vital economic sector that generates significant revenue, employment opportunities, and cultural exchange. However, it also places considerable strain on natural resources and ecosystems. According to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism contributes approximately 8% of global greenhouse gas emissions, mostly through transportation and accommodations. Within the tourism industry, restaurants form an integral part of the overall experience for travelers.

Additionally, research known as the "Green Plan" conducted in Namibia is underway in an effort to mitigate the adverse effects of tourism. The plan includes statements regarding finance, marketing, staff training and education, the establishment of a tourism management information system, organizational structure, and product development. An Environmental Assessment Study will be required of all tourism developers (Mason, P., 2020). Thus, it is crucial for restaurant owners and managers to recognize the impact of their operations and adopt green operation. Trafialek et. al (2019) defines green operation in restaurant as the means of reducing the negative impact on the environment which starts from growing or manufacturing the food until it is consumed. From the discussion of above studies, it

is worth mentioning that there is a clear desire from owners and management to tackle environmental challenges.

However, there is still a lack of instruments to fully implement their vision. This research shows that the restaurant business has to work together to make green practices a top priority and implement all possible strategies for doing so.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Population, Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The population under investigation in this study comprises a wide variety of restaurants that are operational in Bangladesh, with a specific emphasis on establishments situated in Cox's Bazar, a well-known tourist destination. The list of restaurants is sourced from the "District based hotels and accommodation list" provided by the Cox's Bazar District Administration website (Cox's Bazar District Administration, n.d.). The restaurants are selected from Cox's Bazar, a well-acclaimed tourist destination in Bangladesh. To ensure that the sample was representative, a two-stage sampling procedure was utilized. Predominantly, restaurants were classified as "Restaurants with Hotel Facilities" and "General Restaurants" at the outset.

The categorization was predicated on the characteristics and extent of the services provided by every establishment. Following that, establishments were selected from each stratum utilizing a systematic random sampling technique. The convenience sampling approach was used to choose 31 eateries for the sample, with great care taken to guarantee that each stratum was represented proportionally. Data has been collected from February 2022 to May 2022 from the Cox's Bazar, a well-known tourist destination of Bangladesh. It was determined that this sample size was sufficient to accomplish the study's aims while also allowing for practical data collecting and analysis. For the sake of precision and uniformity, all data editing, verification, and cleaning was done inside. In order to make data processing more efficient, numerical coding was used.

3.2. Data Collection Tools and Techniques

The data collecting approach was directed by a well-designed study strategy, which detailed the methodology, tools, and quality assurance techniques. The collection of primary data includes conducting face-to-face interviews with important stakeholders, such as restaurant owners, managers, and staff members who are engaged in making operational decisions. The interviews were designed in a systematic manner to address several subjects, such as knowledge and comprehension of environmentally friendly practices, present approaches to implementation, perceived advantages and obstacles, and future plans for initiatives for environmental sustainability. In addition, standardized questionnaires were used to complement interview replies and collect quantitative data. The surveys consisted of a combination of closed-ended and open-ended questions. The survey used closed-ended questions, such as Likert-scale items, to measure respondents' opinions and views. Additionally, dichotomous questions were included to collect categorical data on specific practices and behaviors. Included in the survey were open-ended questions designed to elicit comprehensive views and qualitative input about many elements of green activities.

3.3. Data Analysis Method

A systematic analytical procedure was used to extract valuable insights and make conclusions from the acquired data. At first, descriptive statistics were used to highlight important results in the quantitative data that was collected from the surveys. This included measures of central tendency, percentages, and frequencies. The data has been analyzed using inferential statistical techniques including Rating and mean. A thematic analysis was performed on the qualitative data collected through interviews and open-ended questionnaires in order to reveal trends, patterns, and recurrent ideas. To make sense of the qualitative data, we used classification algorithms and the Mean Score on Parameters to arrange it. We ensured the reliability and credibility of the study findings by adhering to strong methodological standards throughout the data processing procedure.

3.4.Limitations

The study has a number of limitations that must be recognized despite its contributions to the body of information addressing environmentally friendly practices in restaurants. The problem was first introduced during the interview by some owners and management. Some of them remained silent. Additionally, a number of restaurants have doubts about this kind of scholarly research. They therefore weren't sufficient to offer the needed information. There are numerous more environmentally friendly restaurant practices that are not covered by this study that can be added and evaluated for future studies. Only the importance of green practices to Bangladeshi restaurant owners and management is the subject of this study.

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1.Analysis of profile of the respondents

Profile of the respondents that includes various socioeconomic and demographic data as gender, education level, position in their organization, their experiences, categories of the restaurant, the size of the restaurant etc. are shown (appendix) and discussed.

It is (appendix) revealed that among the respondents the percentage of the male is 100 and no number of female respondents is found. It has occurred for the nature of the industry where no females are involved. In terms of education, 42% of respondents is graduate and 29% is HSC passed. Only 10% is SSC passed and no respondents from primary education are found. In the question of position in the organization, 65 % of respondents is the manager and the remaining (35%) are the owner. In the whole sample, 71% respondents have the experiences of 1 to 5 years and 29% has 6 to 10 years experiences. In case of the type of restaurant, 94% of respondents is from the type of 'restaurant with the hotel' and the rest of the respondents are drawn from the 'general' type of restaurant. In terms of restaurant's size based on the number of employees, 77% respondents are drawn from such restaurants which have the number of employees is from 1 to 20 and 23% respondents have taken from the restaurants where the number of employees is from 21 to 40. In the question of restaurant's size based on monthly average sale 68% respondents are taken from restaurants which have the sale of tk. 1 to 20 lakh and 26% has the sale of tk. 41 to 60 lakh.

4.2. Identifying Green Practice

To check the level of knowledge on green practice the researcher asked the respondents to define the term in the restaurant. The question on this issue was open-ended. Various types of answers are explored from which researcher categorizes these into three types – correct answer, partially correct answer and wrong answer. The answers are categorized based on the operational definition of green practice for this study. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of responses regarding the definition of green practice in restaurant

Category of Answer	Number of respondents	Percentage
Correct Answer	3	9.68
Partially Correct	23	74.19
Wrong Answer	5	16.13
Total	31	100.00

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

The table 1 reflects that about 10% of respondents can define green practice in restaurants correctly. 74% can define the issue partially and 16% of the respondents' definition was totally wrong.

4.3. Whether Green Practice have or not in the restaurants

The researcher places a question on the restaurant owners/management whether they have Green Practice in their organizations. The query was in the form of the dichotomous question. Outcomes are placed in the following table and chart (Table 2 and Figure 1).

Table 2. Distribution of responses regarding whether hotels have green practice

Items/Statement	Yes		No	
	No. of the respondent	Percentage	No. of the respondent	Percentage
Whether there are green practices in the restaurants	26	84	5	16

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Figure 1. Illustrating whether there are green practices in restaurants

The above table (see Table 2) and the figure-1 show that approximately 84% of restaurants have green practices and only 16% have no green exercise.

There are several restaurants which have no any green practices. Why? Various findings are explored on not-adopting even a single practice for green issue through the survey which is listed beneath:

1. The absence of the knowledge on the green matter is one of the vital reasons to implement green issue in the restaurants.
2. Some management thinks that this is not the time to exercise green.
3. To confirm green practice in the restaurant business a big investment is required.
4. Separate management is needed toward green practices in which restaurants' owners and managements are not agreed upon.

4.4. Assessment of Opinion of the Respondents that Green Practice is Important

It is seen that 57.1% respondents from the level of higher education think that Green Practice is important and the remaining 42.9% respondents from primary to mid-level of education (Primary to HSC) provide importance on Green Practice. 64.7% of the respondents of higher education assume that such problem is very important. 35.3% interviewees from primary to mid-level education think that Green Practice is very important (See Table 3).

Table 3. Green Practice * Level of Education Cross tabulation

		Level of education		Total
		Primary-mid (Primary, SSC and HSC)	Higher (Graduate and Post graduate)	
Green practice	important	6 42.9%	8 57.1%	14 100.0%
	very important	6 35.3%	11 64.7%	17 100.0%
Total		12 38.7%	19 61.3%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .185$, df = 1, p value = .475

However, the association between Green Practice and Level of Education is found statistically to be insignificant at 5% level.

Table 4 shows that 64.3% respondents, who are the managers, think that Green Practice is important and the 35.7% respondents are owner give importance to Green Practice. 64.7% of the respondents whose status is manager assume that Green Practice is very important. 35.3% owners believe that such practice is very important.

Table 4. Green Practice * Designation of the respondents' Cross tabulation

		Designation of the respondent		Total
		Owner	Manager	
Green practice	important	5 35.7%	9 64.3%	14 100.0%
	very important	6 35.3%	11 64.7%	17 100.0%
Total		11 35.5%	20 64.5%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .001$, df = 1, p value = .636

It is found that 78.6% respondents with 1 to 5 years experiences, involved restaurant business believe that Green Practice is important and the remaining 21.24% respondents, who have 6 to more than 6 years experiences, give importance on Green Practice. On the other hand, among 17 respondents 64.7% with 1 to 5 years experiences, think that Green Practice is very important and 35.3% interviewees who belongs to 6 to more than 6 years experiences assume that Green Practice is very important (See Table 5).

Table 5. Green Practice * Experiences of the respondents' Cross tabulation

		Experiences of the respondents		Total
		1 to 5 years	6 to 10 years	
Green practice	important	11 78.6%	3 21.24%	14 100.0%
	very important	11 64.7%	6 35.3%	17 100.0%
Total		22 71.0%	9 29.0%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .716$, df = 1, p value = .329

Table 6 demonstrates that 92.9% respondents from the type of the restaurant with hotel think that Green Practice is important and only 7.1% of the respondents from general type assume that the practice is important. 94.1% respondents from the restaurant with hotel believe that Green Practice is very important and only 5.9% respondents of general type believe that such issue is very important.

Table 6. Green Practice * Type of restaurant Cross tabulation

		Type of restaurant		Total
		General	Restaurant with hotel	
Green practice	important	1 7.1%	13 92.9%	14 100.0%
	very important	1 5.9%	16 94.1%	17 100.0%
Total		2 6.5%	29 93.5%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .020$, df = 1, p value = .708

The association between Green Practice and Type of Restaurant is statistically tested and found to be insignificant.

Table 7 shows that 71.4% respondents who have 1 to 20 employees in their restaurant assume that Green Practice is important and 28.6% respondents who have 21 to 40 employees give importance to Green Practice. 82.4% of the respondents having 1 to 20 employees think that Green Practice is very important. 17.6% interviewees with 21 to 40 employees believe that Green Practice is very important.

Table 7. Green Practice * Number of Employees Cross tabulation

		Number of employees		Total
		1 to 20 employees	21 to 40 employees	
Green practice	important	10 71.4%	4 28.6%	14 100.0%
	very important	14 82.4%	3 17.6%	17 100.0%
Total		24 77.4%	7 22.6%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .524$, df = 1, p value = .383

The association between Green Practice and Number of Employees in the restaurant is statistically tested and found to be insignificant.

It is vivid that 64.3% respondents of the restaurant, which monthly average sale is tk. 1 to 20 lakh, think that Green Practice is important and 35.7% respondents, in which monthly average sale is tk. 41 to 60 lakh, provide importance on Green Practice. 70.6% of the respondents of the restaurant which monthly average sale is tk. 1 to 20 lakh assume that such issue is very important. 11.8% restaurants' monthly average sale is tk. 21 to 40 lakh think that Green Practice is very important and 17.6% interviewees of restaurant with monthly average sale of tk. 41 to 60 lakh assume that the practice is very important (See Table 8).

Table 8. Green Practice * Monthly Average Sales Cross tabulation

		Monthly average sales (in taka)			Total
		1 to 20 Lakh	21 to 40 Lakh	41 to 60 Lakh	
Green practice	important	9 64.3%	0 0%	5 35.7%	14 100.0%
	very important	12 70.6%	2 11.8%	3 17.6%	17 100.0%
Total		21 67.7%	2 6.5%	8 25.8%	31 100.0%

Type of test $\chi^2 = .2663$, df = 2, p value = .264

4.5. Rating of the Different Dimensions

In green practice to the restaurants, several dimensions are considered. Among these dimensions to evaluate eight tentative related dimensions were placed before the restaurant's management with a request to rate their choices. The dimensions were green Practices, recycling program, composting program, energy savings program, water conservation program, eco-friendly cleaning supplies, menu offered and procurement.

A prearranged questionnaire with five-point rating scale was used for the purpose where the rating could vary from 'Very Important' (carrying a score of 5) to 'Completely Unimportant' (carrying a score of 1). The outcomes of the entire exercise are shown and explained below.

4.5.1. Green Practices

The following table (See Table 9) shows the ratings of the dimension parameter of 'Green Practices' by the sample restaurants.

Table 9. Rating of the parameter ‘Green Practices’

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	18	58	90
Important	4	13	42	52
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	0	0	0
Completely unimportant	1	0	0	0
Total		31	100	142
Mean Score		4.58		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

The rating of ‘Green Practices’ in the restaurant as a dimension parameter by the sample restaurant-management. It is observed from the above table that 58% of the sample rated ‘Green Practices’ as ‘Very important’ followed by 42% of the sample rated the parameter as ‘Important’. The mean score of the respondents’ rating of ‘Green Practices’ is 4.58, which reflects that ratings of the respondents are near about ‘Very important’ (See Table 9).

4.5.2. Recycling Program

Table beneath (See Table 10) shows the ratings of the dimension parameter by ‘Recycling Program’ by the sample restaurant-management.

Table 10. Restaurants’ rating of the parameter ‘Recycling Program’

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	9	29	45
Important	4	14	45	56
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	8	26	16
Completely unimportant	1	0		0
Total		31	100	117
Mean Score		3.77		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

The table 10 presents the rating of ‘Recycling Program’ as a dimension parameter by the sample restaurant-management in Cox’s Bazar. It is observed from the table that 45% of the sample restaurants rated the parameter as ‘Important’ followed by 29% of the sample restaurants rated that program as ‘Very important’. 26% of respondents think that this program is ‘Unimportant’. The mean score of the respondents’ ratings of ‘Recycling Program’ is 3.77, which reflects that ratings of the respondents are near about ‘Important’.

4.5.3. Composting Program

Table 11 shows the ratings of the dimension parameter by ‘Composting Program’ by the sample restaurants.

Table 11. Rating of parameter ‘Composting Program’

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	0	0	0

Important	4	17	55	68
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	12	39	24
Completely unimportant	1	2	6	2
Total		31	100	94
Mean Score		3.03		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 11 reveals the rating of ‘Composting Program’ as a dimension of green practices by sample restaurants. It is observed from the above table that 55% of the sample restaurants are of the opinion that ‘Composting Program’ is ‘Important’. 39% rated the program as ‘Unimportant’ followed by 6% rated as ‘Completely unimportant’. The mean score of the respondents’ ratings of ‘Composting Program’ is 3.03. It is evident from the mean score that the ratings of the respondents are in ‘Neither important nor unimportant’.

4.5.4. Energy Savings Program

The following table (See Table 12) exhibits the ratings of the dimension parameter, in green tourism practices, by ‘Energy Savings Program’ by the sample restaurants.

Table 12. Rating of parameter ‘Energy Savings Program’ by restaurant-management

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	29	94	145
Important	4	2	6	8
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	0	0	0
Completely unimportant	1	0	0	0
Total		31	100	153
Mean Score		4.93		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 12 presents the rating of ‘Energy Savings Program’ as a dimension parameter in practicing green in Cox’s Bazar by sample restaurants. It is viewed from the table that 94% of the sample restaurants rated the program as ‘Very important’, followed by 6% rated the parameter as ‘Important’. The mean score of the interviewees’ rating of ‘Energy Savings Program’ is 4.93, which reflects that ratings of the respondents are near about ‘Very important’.

4.5.5. Water conservation program

Table 13 demonstrates the ratings of the dimension parameter by ‘Water Conservation Program’ by the sample restaurants.

Table 13. Restaurants’ rating of the parameter by ‘Water Conservation Program’

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	2	7	10
Important	4	15	48	60
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	14	45	28

Completely unimportant	1	0	0	0
Total		31	100	98
Mean Score		3.16		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 13 presents the rating of 'Water Conservation Program' as a dimension by the sample restaurants. It is examined from the above table that 48% of the respondents rated 'Water Conservation Program' as 'Important' to exercise green and 45% rated as 'Unimportant'. The dimension parameter is rated by the respondents as 'Very important' which percentage is 7. The mean score of the respondents' ratings of the parameter is 3.16 means that ratings are near about 'Neither importation nor unimportant'.

4.5.6. Eco-friendly cleaning supplies

Table underneath (See Table 14) exhibits the rating of the dimension parameter by 'Eco-friendly Cleaning Supplies' by the sample respondents.

Table 14. Rating of Parameter 'Eco-friendly Cleaning Supplies'

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	5	16	25
Important	4	19	61	76
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	7	23	14
Completely unimportant	1	0	0	0
Total		31	100	115
Mean Score		3.70		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 14 conveys the rating of 'Eco-friendly Cleaning Supplies' as a dimension parameter by the sample respondents. It is surveyed from the above table that 61% of the sample restaurants rated the parameter as 'Important' followed by 16% of the sample respondents rated as 'Very important'. It is also apparent that 23% of the respondents rated the program as 'Unimportant'. The mean score of the respondents' ratings of 'Eco-friendly Cleaning Supplies' is 3.70, which reflects that ratings of the respondents are near 'Important'.

4.5.7. Menu offered

Table 15 reveals the ratings of the dimension parameter by 'Manu Offered' by the sample respondents.

Table 15. Rating of parameter 'Menu Offered' by Restaurants

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	11	36	55
Important	4	19	61	76
Neither important nor unimportant	3	0	0	0
Unimportant	2	1	3	2
Completely unimportant	1	0	0	0
Total		31	100	133
Mean Score		4.29		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 15 presents the rating of ‘Menu Offered’ as a dimension parameter of exercising green by the sample respondents. It is checked from the above table that 61% of the respondents rated ‘Menu Offered’ as ‘Important’ followed by 36% of sample restaurants rated the specific parameter as ‘Very important’. Only 3% respondents rated the dimension parameter as ‘Unimportant’. The mean score of the respondents’ ratings of ‘Menu Offered’ is 4.29 means that ratings are near about ‘Important.’

4.5.8. Procurement

Table 16 shows the ratings of the dimension parameter by ‘Procurement’ by the sample restaurant-management.

Table 16. Restaurants’ rating of the parameter ‘Procurement’

Rating	Rating score (assigned)	Frequency	Percent of all respondents	Total score (Col. 2 x Col. 3)
Very important	5	2	7	10
Important	4	14	45	56
Neither important nor unimportant	3	1	3	3
Unimportant	2	13	42	26
Completely unimportant	1	1	3	1
Total		31	100	96
Mean Score		3.09		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 16 presents the rating of ‘Procurement’ as a dimension parameter by the sample restaurant-management in Cox’s Bazar. It is observed from the table that 45% of the sample restaurants rated the program as ‘Important’ followed by 42% of the sample restaurants rated that program as ‘Unimportant’. 7% of respondents think that this program is ‘Very important’. The mean score of the respondents’ ratings of ‘Procurement’ is 3.09, which reflects that ratings of the respondents are in ‘Neither important nor unimportant’.

4.6. Dimensions Considered Important by the Respondents

Keeping the eight selected dimension used for rating of restaurants, the sample respondents were asked which of these dimensions they especially considered with importance toward green practices in their organizations. The responses were to be calculated against eight dimensions in a mean score format through Likert rating scale.

Table 17. Mean Score on Parameters of Green Practices

Serial No	Parameters	Mean
I	Green Practice	4.58
II	Recycling Program	3.77
III	Composting Program	3.03
IV	Energy Savings Program	4.93
V	Water Conservation Program	3.16
VI	Eco-friendly Cleaning Supplies	3.70
VII	Manu Offered	4.29
VIII	Procurement	3.09
N= 31		

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Table 17 presents the summary of restaurants’ ratings of the dimension parameters. It is observed from the above table that out of eight-dimension parameters, the restaurant-management were found in giving

importance at varying degrees on the three dimensions as energy savings program, green practices and menu offered.

The rating of the restaurant-management in the above-mentioned dimension parameters are in the range of 'Important' to 'Very important'.

5. Major Findings

- Understanding of Green Practice Definitions

Only 9.68% of those who answered correctly described what "green practice" meant.

A majority (74.19%) gave partly right definitions, which shows that people were not all aware of the issue.

- Adoption of Green Practices

84% of businesses polled said they were environmentally friendly.

Shows that a lot of people are putting sustainable projects into action.

- Barriers to Adoption

Problems included not knowing enough and thinking the costs were too high.

People thought that having separate management for green practices would be hard.

- Importance of Green Practice

People with more schooling and managers were more likely to value green methods.

People with less experience also understood how important it was.

- Dimensions Considered Important

Green methods, food items, and programs that save energy were emphasized.

The fact that these categories got higher mean scores shows how important they are.

Overall, the significance of green practices is becoming more widely acknowledged. Prioritizing important aspects and removing obstacles to adoption required effort.

6. Discussion

According to data analysis on restaurant owners and managers' knowledge of green practices (Identifying green practices), the majority of them theoretically are unable to do so. It affects how this kind of practice is carried out. Despite the fact that they lack theoretical knowledge, they have a number of practices in their businesses. These practices have been identified in part. It is clear from the analyses that there isn't even a single practice for the green issue in many restaurants due to a variety of reasons, including a lack of knowledge, a lack of time to practice green, the need for investment, and the need for separate management. The significance of green practices to owners and managers is measured, and the results vary. Based on the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of the respondents, data interpretation from the Chi-square test reveals a variety of intriguing findings to determine the level of importance of green practices to the restaurant business. Statistics show that the relationship between green practices and educational attainment is negligible at the 5% level. Higher educated respondents emphasize the significance of green practices in this choice. Managers are given priority over owners at both importance levels (important and very important). Green practices are either important or very important, according to respondents with between one and five years of experience in the restaurant industry. Restaurant type and green practices Cross-tabulation reveals that the "restaurant with hotel" category believes green practices are either essential or extremely crucial. The restaurants with a minimum of 1 to 20 employees have a positive signal about the importance (whether important or very important) of green practices. Another finding is that restaurants with monthly average sales between 1 and 20 lakh (bdt) believe that green practices are crucial or extremely crucial. The importance of eight parameters is determined by the respondents' responses. The majority of respondents view the topic of "green practices" as substantial (important or extremely important). According to the replies, recycling

and composting programs are vital for exercising environmentally friendly practices, and some people believe that they are highly important. The procurement situation clearly follows the same pattern. The majority of respondents (94%) believe that energy saving initiatives are vital for green practices. The owners and managers recognize the importance of the composting program, but they don't consider it to be very important.

7. Conclusion and Recommendation

The restaurant industry can be a significant player in green tourism attempts. Although restaurant owners and management are unable to define green practices in tourism, it is clear from this survey that they do have certain green practices in place inside their organizations. Many restaurants skip out on green practices for a variety of reasons. The primary barriers to being green in restaurants are mostly a lack of understanding of the issue, a lack of understanding of how to apply green practices, a refusal to make investments for this purpose, and skepticism regarding the benefits of the activities. The restaurant industry should prioritize real-world green concerns in order to gain a competitive edge and join similar sectors in green initiatives. The government and associations should take steps toward educating the restaurant sector on the meaning of the term "green practice" and to persuade them of the advantages that it has for both their particular business and the environment as a whole.

8. Further Research Direction

Given that environmental pollution is a serious concern, the entire world is currently moving forward with environmentally friendly approaches to reduce pollution. The researcher ignores the restaurant industry's urgent requirement for applications and genuine practices of environmentally friendly methods. Performance is a variable that needs to be looked into while discussing applications. This study's flaw is that it should have tested the effectiveness of green practices through research. The genuine green practices of the restaurant in Bangladesh might be investigated through further study. In the future, academics may take the initiative to examine the importance and performance of green practices in this industry.

Appendix. The socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	31	100	Designation	Owner	11	35
	Female	0	0		Manager	20	65
	Total=	31	100		Total=	31	100
Experiences in this business (in year)	1 - 5	22	71	Restaurant size (based on number of employees)	1 - 20	24	77
	6 -10	9	29		21 - 40	7	23
	Total=	31	100		Total=	31	100
Type of restaurant	General	2	6	Restaurant's size (based on monthly average sale) Total	Tk. 1 – 20 lakh	21	68
	Restaurant with hotel	29	94		Tk. 21 – 40 lakh	2	6
	Total=	31	100		Tk. 41 – 60 lakh	8	26
					Total=	31	100
Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)	Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Level of Education	Primary	0	0	Level of Education	Graduate	13	42

	SSC	3	10		Post Graduate	6	19
	HSC	9	29		Total=	19	61
	Total=	12	39				
					Total=	31 (12 + 19)	100 (39 + 61)

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2022

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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